

A Review of Cluster Analysis Techniques and Their Uses in Library and Information Science Research: K-Means and K-Medoids Clustering

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Abstract

Purpose. This study explores the definitions and characteristics of cluster analysis, a machine-learning technique that is frequently implemented to identify groupings in big datasets, and its applicability to LIS research. This overview is intended for researchers who are interested in expanding their data analysis repertory to include cluster analysis, rather than for existing experts in this area.

Design. A review of LIS articles included in the Library and Information Source (EBSCO) database that employ cluster analysis is performed. An overview of cluster analysis in general (how it works from a statistical standpoint, and how it can be performed by researchers), the most popular cluster analysis techniques, and the uses of cluster analysis in LIS research is presented.

Findings. The number of LIS studies that employ a cluster analytic technique has grown from about 5 studies per year in the early 2000s to an average of 35 studies per year in the mid- and late-2010s. The journal *Scientometrics* has the most articles published within LIS that use cluster analysis (102 studies). *Scientometrics* is the most common subject area to employ a cluster analytic technique (152 studies). The findings of this review indicate that cluster analysis could make LIS research more accessible by providing an innovative and insightful process of knowledge discovery.

Originality. This review is the first to present cluster analysis—specifically from a LIS perspective—as an approachable data analysis technique.

Data come in many forms. A collection of datasets can mostly be analyzed to produce novel insights. Over the past century, as computers have evolved in speed and capacity, new machine-learning techniques have emerged that allow researchers to discover hidden patterns or new knowledge beyond what traditional statistical analyses could procure. While underutilized in Library and Information Science (LIS) research, particularly research related to information provision and library services, these approaches hold great potential for better understandings LIS issues from information technology adoption to reading habits to library circulation trends (Cordell, 2020; Lund, 2020). This review focuses on one type of machine-learning technique, cluster analysis, which classifies and sorts datasets into groups, or clusters, based on a similarity measure. This method, sharing some commonalities with content analysis (using automated procedures rather than manual ones), may be used in LIS research to identify patterns and logical groupings in big datasets that would otherwise be untenable to analyze manually.

What is Cluster Analysis?

Cluster analysis is a common data mining process that identifies latent patterns and groupings in a dataset (Hardle & Simar, 2019; Ma & Lund, 2020; Romesburg, 2004). It evolved over the period of nearly a century of computerization and machine-learning development (Jain, 2008). Cluster analysis is an example of an unsupervised machine-learning procedure, where patterns among data are identified without input from the user (e.g., providing some type of ontology with which the algorithm could classify data) (Kettenring, 2006).

Two of the most common types of cluster analysis are *k-means* and *k-medoids*. These two heuristic methods share many similarities, with one key distinction. In both techniques, the researchers/analyst must define the value of “*k*,” the number of

clusters to be calculated. The number selected may be based on a theory or hypothesis, a statistical estimation, or through trial-and-error. Both approaches will then assign all values in a dataset to one of the k clusters.

The *k-means* algorithm begins by creating k number of clusters, then sorting each data point into the cluster with the nearest mean value. In the initial iteration, the clusters will often be very imperfect, as the “means” are, more-or-less, arbitrarily defined by the algorithm. After all the points have been assigned to a cluster, new mean values are calculated within the clusters. Data points are then reassigned to the new cluster with the nearest mean value. This process continues through new iterations until the mean values of the previous iteration of clusters and current iteration are near identical. Two examples of this process are shown in Figure 1. Calculations, obviously, would become exponentially more complex as the size of the dataset grows, making it increasingly difficult to cluster data manually. Fortunately, this process is all done automatically by the algorithm, with the system/software the researcher/analyst uses only reporting the final result.

For a dataset {12, 94, 72, 19, 3, 46, 16, 77, 61, 53, 25, 31}

Round 1:

- Cluster 1—value of 6: 3, 12, 16, 19
- Cluster 2—value of 40: 25, 31, 46, 53
- Cluster 3—value of 80: 61, 72, 77, 94

Round 2:

- Cluster 1—mean value of 12.5: 3, 12, 16, 19, 25
- Cluster 2—mean value of 38.75: 31, 46, 53
- Cluster 3—mean value of 76: 61, 72, 77, 94

Round 3:

- Cluster 1—mean value of 15: 3, 12, 16, 19, 25
 - Cluster 2—mean value of 43: 31, 46, 53
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- Cluster 3—mean value of 76: 61, 72, 77, 94

Cluster 1 contains low values, cluster 2 contains middle values, and cluster 3 contains high values.

For a dataset with multiple values, such as {(45, 41), (27, 5), (12, 31), (11, 25), (44, 10), (22, 25), (38, 2), (5, 28), (15, 20), (26, 1), (36, 42), (19, 17)}, the shortest combined distance is used.

Round 1:

- Cluster 1—value of (43, 29): (45, 41), (36, 42)
- Cluster 2—value of (45, 12): (27, 5), (44, 10), (38, 2), (26, 1)
- Cluster 3—value of (22, 26): (12, 31), (11, 25), (22, 25), (5, 28), (15, 20), (9, 17)

Round 2:

- Cluster 1—mean value (40.5, 41.5): (45, 41), (36, 42)
- Cluster 2—mean value (33.75, 4.5): (27, 5), (44, 10), (38, 2), (26, 1)
- Cluster 3—mean value (12.3, 24.3): (12, 31), (11, 25), (22, 25), (5, 28), (15, 20), (9, 17)

Cluster 1 contains datapoints where both values are high, cluster 2 contains points where the first value is high and the second value is low, and cluster 3 contains points where the first value is low and the second value is high.

Figure 1. Example of *k-means* Cluster Process

k-medoids clustering is quite similar to *k-means* clustering, with both using the same partitioning technique based on closeness. However, unlike *k-means*, which clusters around mean values, *k-medoids* clusters around “medoids,” existing data points that exemplify the relationships among the data in each cluster. A *k-medoids* clustering of the same data from the first example in Figure 1 is shown in Figure 2. The size of the final clusters differs based on the *k-means* versus *k-medoids* techniques, with the *k-means* analysis producing a “low value” cluster with 5 data points, and “mid value” cluster with 3 points, and a “high value” cluster with 4 points, while the *k-medoids* analysis produced clusters of size 4, 5, and 3, respectively.

For a dataset {12, 94, 72, 19, 3, 46, 16, 77, 61, 53, 25, 31}

Round 1:

- Cluster 1—value of 6: 3, 12, 16, 19
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- Cluster 2—value of 40: 25, 31, 46, 53
 - Cluster 3— value of 80: 61, 72, 77, 94

Round 2:

- Cluster 1— medoid value of 3: 3, 12, 16, 19
 - Cluster 2— medoid value of 46: 25, 31, 46, 53, 61
 - Cluster 3— medoid value of 77: 72, 77, 94
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Figure 2. Example of *k-medoids* Clustering Process

Both *k-means* and *k-medoids* cluster analysis can be used with either numerical or text data. For text data, the algorithm clusters data based on word frequencies within each item/data point, then clusters based on these frequencies. In this sense, it shares similarities to content analysis, though it is automated and based on statistical principles rather than based on the judgment of the researchers as to the appropriate classification.

Table 1 compares the strengths and limitations of the *k-means* and *k-medoids* techniques. Both techniques are commonly used by scholarly researchers and data scientists, but they are not used interchangeably. *K-means* should be used primarily in cases where the dataset is normally distributed (similar to how one would only want to use the mean value in this case), while *k-medoids* should be used when data is undesirably skewed or contains outliers. One must understand the data itself in order to select the appropriate technique.

K-Means	K-Medoids
Selects the true mean of each cluster, even if the value does not actually match that of any member of the cluster	Selects an exemplar from the actual cluster that best approximates the true mean of that cluster
Similar to finding the “mean” within datasets	Similar to finding the “median” within datasets
Better for normally distributed data without outliers	Better for datasets with large skew or outliers
Also appropriate for analyses where	Not appropriate for analyses where

outliers are considered important to include in the clustering	outliers are considered important (they will be, essentially, nullified)
More significant for data that are not likely to naturally fall into discrete categories (e.g., enrollment numbers for classes)	More significant for data that is likely to naturally fall into discrete categories (e.g., number of scholarly publications/citations by faculty)
More common of the two techniques	More reliable of the two techniques

Table 1. Strengths and Limitations of K-Means and K-Medoids Techniques

Conducting Cluster Analysis

Cluster analysis is convenient to use with large, existing datasets, such as the *Public Library Survey (PLS)* by *Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS)* or the *Integrated Postsecondary Education Data (IPEDS)* by *National Center for Educational Statistics (NCES)*, as a form of secondary data analysis. There are a number of ways to perform a cluster analysis: there is a tool within IBM's *SPSS* to perform basic cluster analyses, the statistical software package *R* includes compatibility with libraries that allow for advanced cluster analyses, and the software *RapidMiner* offers an intuitive user interface while providing the same analytical capabilities as *R*. Data for any of these platforms may be created and stored in an Excel spreadsheet (as a *xls* or *csv* file) before being transferred to any of these other platforms for analysis.

R

As *R* is a free software, as opposed to *SPSS* (a licensed software) and *RapidMiner* (i.e., a paid software with a free option for academics), *R* is perhaps the most widely-used software for cluster analysis. *R Studio* (<https://rstudio.com/>) provides an environment—very similar to an HTML programming environment like Visual Studio—where the researcher can import data, execute a cluster analysis, and visualize research findings. Generally, the use of *R* does require technical knowledge of the *R* programming language, however one does not need to be “fluent” in *R* in

order to use the platform for a specific purpose like performing a cluster analysis. The following procedure will allow a researcher to retrieve a dataset and perform a *k-means* cluster analysis in *R* (i.e., assuming that the spreadsheet holding the data is formatted properly into columns):

1. Enter: `> DatasetName=read.csv("Desktop/Filename.csv")`, where "DatasetName" is the placeholder name you want to use for your dataset within *R* (like a variable) and "Filename.csv" is the name of the file/spreadsheet that holds your data.
2. Enter: `> results <- kmeans(DatasetName, k)`, where "k" is the number of clusters you want to identify from the dataset.
3. Enter: `> results`, to display the results within *R*. This will present the size of each cluster (i.e., how many rows/observations fit within each) as well as the mean values within each cluster for each of the variables.
4. You may then also explore more specific features of the cluster analysis result, by specifying a component you would like to explore in more detail (e.g., "centers" entered as `> results$centers` tells the researcher the central value of each cluster).

RapidMiner

RapidMiner studio is a free software for data mining. *RapidMiner* uses a drag-and-drop interface that simplifies the process of performing a cluster analysis compared to the coding needed for *R*. The default work environment (which can be customized) includes five boxes: one tall rectangular box in the center, which displays the process to be performed (where users "drop" the operators); two stacked square boxes on the left, with the top box used to import the data to be analyzed and the bottom box used to select operators. From the operators box menu, one can either

scroll to or search for the *k-means* or *k-medoids* cluster analysis operators. This operator can then be dragged to the center box and a connection drawn between it and the imported data. This looks similar to the diagram in Figure 3. The two stacked boxes on the right side of the interface include a parameters box (this is where the “k” number of clusters would be specified, for instance), and a help box that provides information about any item selected by the user. This software still requires a fair amount of technical know-how but eliminates the coding element.

<FIGURE 3 ABOUT HERE>

SPSS

SPSS perhaps has the most straightforward process for performing a cluster analysis. Within *SPSS*, the cluster analysis options can be found under “classify” in the *Analyze* tab. These options will head to a dialog where the variables to be included in cluster analysis may be selected as well as the number of clusters. The output provided by *SPSS* shows the cluster centers through each iteration and the final cluster centers (the “means” in the case of *k-means*), as well as the number of cases/data points in each cluster.

Cluster Analysis in LIS Research

Methods

From the database Library and Information Science Source (EBSCO), 495 articles were identified that utilized cluster analysis, published through the year 2020. No beginning date was defined but cluster analysis was first developed in the 1930s so this sets a de facto beginning period. These articles were retrieved by searching for “*clustering*,” “*cluster analysis*,” “*k-means*,” “*k-medoids*,” and then validating each article to ensure they did, in fact, utilize a clustering technique. Bibliographic data were then collected from these articles, including publication year, journal, and the

article full-texts. Publication years were used to track the number of clustering articles published over time, to track trends. Journal data was collected to analyze which journals publish the most/are the most welcoming to articles that utilize clustering techniques. Full-texts were collected so that the two authors could sort the articles in categories based on the central topic; this allowed the researchers to illustrate which topic areas have traditionally been host to clustering studies and where opportunities lie for future use of clustering techniques.

Findings

Figure 4 displays the number of articles each year that employed a type of cluster analysis, beginning with the first two articles published in 1973. Although the first articles appeared in the 1970s, the number did not begin to jump until the start of the new millennium. From 1970–1979, three articles used cluster analysis; from 1980–1989, 4 were published; 8 were published from 1990–1999; from 2000–2009, 97 of these articles were published; from 2010–2019, this number jumped all the way to 344 articles.

<INSERT FIGURE 4 ABOUT HERE>

Figure 4. Number of Cluster Analysis LIS Articles Over Time

Table 2 displays the ten journals with the most articles that employ cluster analysis. *Scientometrics* has, by far, published the most of these articles of any journals. All of the journals on this list are generally considered to have an “information science” focus, while lacking any focus on libraries. Some of the LIS journals that do have multiple cluster analysis include *Journal of Documentation* (9), *Information Research* (8), *Library Management* (4), *Journal of the Medical Libraries Association* (3), and *Knowledge Organization* (3).

Journal	Count
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Scientometrics	102
Journal of the Association for Information Science & Technology	52
Information Processing & Management	41
Journal of Medical Internet Research	34
Journal of Informetrics	19
Journal of Information Science	16
Journal of the China Society for Scientific & Technical Information	14
Behaviour & Information Technology	12
International Journal of Information Management	12
Health Informatics Journal	11

Table 2. Top Ten LIS Journals by Cluster Analysis Studies Published

Table 3 shows the 495 articles clustered into seven primary subject areas, based on the content of the articles and type of data being analyzed. Bibliographic data was the most common for these studies, followed by data related to information systems operations and retrieval. Some of the areas with the least utilization of the method include library operations and information behavior. Examples of articles in each of these seven subject areas are discussed below.

General Topic Area	Count
Scientometrics and Scholarly Communication	152
Information Systems and Retrieval	135
Library Operations	73
Medical/Health	59
Social Media	37
Information Behavior	26
Data Mining Approaches	13

Table 3. Topic Areas for Cluster Analysis Studies with Frequencies

Scientometrics and Scholarly Communication

Janssens, Leta, Glanzel, and De Moor (2006) mapped six topic clusters based on text content in prominent LIS journal articles. These clusters were identified as (1) patent analysis, (2) and (3) bibliometrics 1 and 2 (two distinct clusters, both centered on bibliometrics topics), (4) webometrics, (5) information retrieval, and (6) “social” or miscellaneous information use studies. Based on topicality, patent analysis was the most disparate category, without a natural LIS journal with which it aligns (as opposed to *Scientometrics* for the topic of bibliometrics, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology (JASIST)*, and *Information Processing and Management (IPM)* for information retrieval, and *Journal of Documentation (J. Doc)*, *JASIST*, and *Journal of Information Science* for webometrics and social topics).

Claudio-González, Martín-Baranera, and Villarroya (2016) utilized a cluster-analytic technique to classify the business models used by academic journals. Four clusters were identified: (1) one that has a larger number of subscribers and low amount of external financial support—open access journals that sell advertisements; (2) one that has a large number of subscribers and high amount of external support—journals that rely on institutional funding; (3) one with mixed funding—open access journals that rely on grants/donations in addition to advertisements or institutional funding; and (4) one that relies heavily on commercial transactions to remain financially viable—journal with a traditional publishing model.

Lund and Maurya (2021) compared the research productivity of LIS researchers based on publications and citations using *k-means* cluster analysis. While they found that researchers in both countries could be sorted into three-tier clusters – low publications/low citations, high publications/high citations, and low publications/high citations – more researchers in India fell into the low publications/low citations cluster and few fell into the low publications/high citations

cluster. Researchers from India had to create a much greater output, on average, to reach the same number of citations as researchers from the United States.

Information Systems and Retrieval

Marcial and Hemminger (2010) examined attributes of scientific data repositories using cluster analysis. Identification of important, distinctive attributes of these repositories was made, with funding support, repository size, and preservation policy being some of the more distinctive attributes. Holding size, for instance, allowed for the 100 repositories studied to be divided into the three clusters of small/less broad (16 of the repositories), medium/broad (24), and large/more broad (60). These unequally-sized clusters illustrate the aim of cluster analysis to classify based on greatest distinction among groups rather than in order to create equally-sized groups.

Kwon and Johnson (2013) examined security policy and data for 250 healthcare organization systems, clustering systems based on adoption of security practices, breach incidents, and compliance with security laws. The researchers identified three clusters (“leaders,” “followers,” and “laggards”) by which to classify the systems. As indicated partly by the terminology used by these researchers, cluster analysis can be used readily with theories that classify things, such as the adopter categories in the *Diffusion of Innovations*. With their study, Kwon and Johnson (2013) found a category of innovators, early adopters, and laggards. Perhaps if they had sought to identify five clusters, they would have identified more-defined early and late majority groups as well. Beyond Kwon and Johnson (2013), the use of cluster analysis for diffusion research is further evidenced in studies like Schedler et al. (2019) and Poba-Nzaou et al. (2020).

Medical/Health

Guillamet et al. (2018) utilize clustering methods to analyze electronic health records, identifying clusters of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) patients. These clusters, if utilized by medical professionals, could help with diagnosis and treatment of comorbidities commonly experienced by patients. O’Neill et al. (2019) performed a cluster analysis on caller data from a mental health call line to classify types of callers. This analysis, similarly, has meaningful practical ramifications, as it may be used to prepare call line operators for the types of callers with whom they can anticipate to interact, and enable earlier diagnosis of mental health emergencies. As demonstrated from these two examples, most of the health informatics studies that utilize cluster analysis use health records in order to identify classifications that may accelerate or improve the accuracy of diagnosis and treatment of medical conditions.

Library Operations

Wang, Tang, Liu, and Li (2011) analyzed academic library resource usage using *k-means* cluster analysis. Based on existing user behavior data, the researchers identified popular resources among users that were relatively lacking in the library’s collections. This offered a different approach to analyzing user need than surveying their opinion—by examining their actual behavior. Based on these findings, the researchers recommended new guidelines for adding resources to the library’s collections.

Jin and He (2017) identified clusters of library patrons based on borrowing behavior, using a sample of 8,556 users at one library and a *k* of 4. Cluster 1 contained 4,364 individuals (over half of the total sample) with a mean per capita borrowing of 7.8 items in one year; cluster 2, with 1,026 individuals, averaged 1.8 items borrowed; cluster 3, with 2482 individuals, borrowed a mean of 19.2 items; and

cluster 4, with 684 individuals, averaged 35 items borrowed. These clusters suggest four very distinct user groups (very low borrowers, low borrowers, moderate borrowers, high borrowers). Compared to simple mean or median values for the entire population—which would be approximately 12.6 and 7.8, respectively—the cluster analysis indicates that there are four distinct groups of borrowers, none of which really borrow anywhere close to 12.6 items a year. In fact, there is a significant population that borrows very few resources and may rather prefer enhanced services or may need better outreach about resources available.

Koizumi and Widdersheim (2019) utilized a hierarchical cluster analysis method to classify models of hiring and management among academic libraries. Seven distinct models/clusters were identified: (1) strategy of higher than average employment of librarians in all specialties; (2) strategy to employ higher than average numbers of electronic resources librarians; (3) strategy to emphasize employment of research and instructional librarians; (4) strategy to emphasize employment of systems librarians; (5) strategy to emphasize employment of instructional librarians only; (6) strategy to emphasize the employment of metadata librarians; and (7) strategy to strengthen general library systems. Both Claudio-Gonzalez et al.(2016) and Koizumi and Widdersheim (2019) concluded that clustering may be helpful in informing library administrative decision-making.

Karunanayake, and Nagata (2014) conducted another library user study that classified undergraduate library users into four clusters based on the variables of search capability, positive image of the library, familiarity with digital resources, usage of professional library assistance, browsing of indexes, and readiness in searching: (1) ineffective library users, (2) effective library users, (3) ineffective but positive users, and (4) self-sufficient users. While ineffective library users rated

poorly on all six measures, effective library users rated highly on all measures except “readiness in searching.” Ineffective but positive users rated high in usage of professional library assistance and browsing of indexes, but low in the other four measures. Self-sufficient users, conversely, rated highly on these four measures but low in usage of professional library assistance and browsing of indexes.

Different variants of cluster analysis have also been used to analyze results from LibQual assessments (Cook et al., 2003; Ennis et al., 2013; Voorbij, 2012). This type of analysis can be useful for organizational insights (how to classify people who use this specific library), even if the results are not published in a scholarly article. Cluster analysis—using the techniques discussed in this paper—can be one of the easier methods to reveal new insights from library assessment data and offers the analyst considerable flexibility in terms of what data will be analyzed and what the quantity and size of clusters will look like.

Social Media

Social media is becoming an increasingly popular source for cluster analysis. Ruas et al. (2019) utilized a cluster analysis to classify the activity of Facebook user profiles into the clusters of “viewer” (who largely only consumes information), “participant” (who engages in both consuming and producing information/content), and “content producer” (who largely creates information with minimal consumption of information created by others). Skovsgaard and Van Dalen (2013), conversely, explore why and how people—specifically, politicians—use social media to communicate information. Three clusters of social media users among politicians were identified: (traditional) mass media users, limited social media users, and heavy social media users. At the time this study was published (2013), it would have been difficult to imagine the importance that social media would play in the rise of some

politicians, while only being adopted to a limited extent by others, but the authors' analysis does pinpoint both of these groups.

Information Behavior

Palsdottir (2010) used *k-means* cluster analysis to sort respondents to a survey of purposive information seeking into four clusters: passive information seekers, moderately passive seekers, moderately active seekers, and active seekers. The largest group of information seekers were passive seekers (n=340 across the two versions of the survey administered), followed by moderately active seekers (217), active seekers (161), and moderately passive seekers (142). By breaking respondents into these four groups, the researcher can better analyze the demographics of each, revealing novel insight about the relationship between demographics and information seeking behavior. For instance, men tended to be more in the passive groups, while women appeared more frequently in the active groups (though in neither case did all participants of one sex appear only in one cluster); younger adults were more frequently in the active groups, while older adults tended to be in more passive groups; and those with more advanced education also tended to be more active seekers of information.

Al-Sammarie et al (2017) also classified information seeking based on cluster analysis. These researchers used eye-tracking analysis of information-seeking and clustered participants based on personality attributes, with three clusters identified: those who have a level of conscientiousness, those who have a high level of agreeableness, and those who have a high level of extraversion. As with Palsdottir's study, the clusters were helpful in identifying relationships between personality groups and information behavior, with those with a high level of conscientiousness

performing the fastest on information-seeking tasks, while members of the other two groups took considerably longer to find information to satisfy their need.

Data Mining Approaches

A few LIS studies utilize cluster analysis as part of developing a new data mining approach or technique that is helpful to library and information services. For example, in Chen and Chen (2007), the authors propose a data mining approach that uses cluster analysis in tandem with other analyses to recommend information resources to users of a digital library. While these types of papers are not common in LIS literature, this subject shows great promise for development within the discipline.

Further Applications of Cluster Analysis for LIS Research

As demonstrated in the above examples, cluster analysis presents a novel approach to secondary data analysis that can be useful in identifying solutions to practical and theoretical problems alike. Any big dataset can be readily sorted into logical categories, whether it be library services data (e.g., number of visitors, circulation, events attended), publications (number of articles published, number of citations per year, age), technology adoption (age, when the technology was adopted, how often it is used), or a myriad of other subjects/types. Given that a lot of data is produced within LIS contexts—whether it be in the course of library operations, taking of censuses about library and information issues (e.g., the *Institute of Museum and Library Services' Public Library Survey*), or empirical research—that is either never analyzed statistically or done so only in the most superficial ways, there is ample opportunity for cluster analysis to be employed as a research technique.

Cluster analysis is useful both for basic and applied research studies (Punj & Steward, 1983), as the groupings can be used to guide theory development (e.g., types of public library spending models) or the development of immediate, practical

solutions (e.g., development of a schema by which to organize books in a collection based on publication date, length, and reputation score). While the procedures to perform a cluster analysis have a bit of a learning curve, once they have been mastered it is quite easy to perform the same analyses again with different datasets. The fact that existing datasets may be used to perform novel analyses makes the process of conducting research more accessible, as opposed to research involving human subjects, which can be tedious with all of the procedures a researcher must following to adhere to ethical and quality guidelines.

Cluster analysis is also appealing in LIS research because it transcends, to some extent, the traditional delineations between the “soft” (e.g., library information provision and services) and “hard” (e.g., computing engineering) science elements of the discipline and demonstrates how computing principles examined by some within the LIS discipline can also be applied in the practical library context to help understand phenomena or develop solutions to persistent problems. In so doing, it helps address some students concerns about “how will I ever use what I am learning in my job.” Using library datasets and basic machine-learning approaches to inform decision-making, as is done in the burgeoning area of “learning analytics” (Jones & Salo, 2017; Oakleaf, Whyte, Lynema, & Brown, 2017), has the potential to make library operations more efficient and supportive to the needs of a diverse collection of patrons.

Conclusion

While cluster analysis as an emerging and evolving secondary data analytic technique may seem challenging to researchers with a limited background in statistical analysis and programming, it is worth learning given its potential value in revealing meaning in large datasets. Unlike statistical approaches like correlation and

regression, which infer relationships among variables, cluster analysis is a statistical technique that groups data, similar to an automated content analysis, to form groupings or ontologies of patterns within the dataset. Therefore, it is promising for LIS researchers to understand the value and importance of cluster analytic techniques and apply it to their respective areas of research interest.

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